

DEVELOPING CAREER INTERESTS OF PRESCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN FUTURE EDUCATORS BASED ON A CULTURAL-HUMANISTIC APPROACH: A METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the methodology for developing career interests of preschool-aged children through digital technologies and a cultural-humanistic approach, as well as the formation of professional-pedagogical culture in future educators. Digital technologies, particularly interactive platforms, toys, and virtual laboratories, are shown to be effective tools for expanding children's knowledge about professions and sparking interest through practical experience. Moreover, the cultural-humanistic approach helps align children's interest in professions with cultural values. Foreign experiences, such as those from the USA, Germany, Finland, Japan, Canada, and Singapore, are analyzed, and the possibility of applying their innovative methods in the national education system is demonstrated. The research also emphasizes how digital technologies can be used to develop the pedagogical culture of educators, highlighting the need for effective methods in the preparation of future teachers through interactive seminars and project-based learning. The article shows that integrating digital technologies and cultural-humanistic approaches helps make the educational process more efficient and enables the educational system to advance to a new level.*

Keywords: *preschool-aged children, profession, interest, development, labor, cultural approach.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, enriching the educational process with innovative technologies is of paramount importance. In the field of preschool education, shaping children's interest in future professions and developing professional-pedagogical culture in future educators is one of the pressing tasks of education. The integration of digital technologies and cultural-humanistic approaches in this process serves to enhance pedagogical effectiveness. This article analyzes the role and methods of digital technologies in developing children's interest in professions and preparing future educators, considering foreign experiences and national specifics.

The topic focuses on two main areas: fostering career interests in preschool-aged children through digital technologies and enhancing the professional-pedagogical culture of future educators using a cultural-humanistic approach.

The development of career interests in preschool-aged children is increasingly recognized as a vital aspect of early education, particularly in the context of a rapidly changing digital landscape. This methodology explores how digital technologies can be harnessed to engage young learners in discovering various professions, fostering their curiosity and creativity from an early

age. Simultaneously, it emphasizes the importance of cultivating a professional-pedagogical culture among future educators through a cultural-humanistic approach. By integrating these two dimensions, the initiative aims to create a dynamic and supportive educational environment that not only prepares children for future career paths but also equips educators with the skills and cultural awareness necessary to guide them effectively.

1. Developing Career Interests in Preschoolers:

- Objective: To stimulate early career interest in young children by leveraging digital technologies.

- Methods: Utilizes interactive tools and educational apps that engage children in exploring various professions. Activities may include role-playing games, virtual field trips, and storytelling that highlight different careers.

- Outcome: Aims to broaden children's understanding of the world of work and help them discover personal interests and talents early on.

2. Enhancing Educators' Professional-Pedagogical Culture:

- Objective: To prepare future educators to effectively guide preschoolers in career exploration, promoting a rich educational environment.

- Cultural-Humanistic Approach: Emphasizes the importance of understanding cultural contexts and individual needs in education. Educators are trained to foster a supportive and inclusive atmosphere that encourages exploration and creativity.

- Professional Development: Involves workshops, reflective practices, and collaboration with experienced educators to build a strong pedagogical foundation.

This methodology aims to create a synergistic relationship between developing children's career interests and equipping educators with the necessary skills and cultural awareness to support this process, ultimately fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment for young children.

Materials and Methods: The research utilized methods such as theoretical analysis, pedagogical observation, experimental trials, and statistical processing. Specifically, foreign and national experiences were studied to develop children's interest in professions and to develop the pedagogical culture of future educators based on the cultural-humanistic approach.

Results and Discussion

The Role of Digital Technologies in Shaping Children's Interest in Professions
Digital technologies are effective tools for expanding children's knowledge about professions and engaging them through practical games.

Foreign Experience:

USA: Through the platform "Career Exploration for Kids", children conduct virtual analyses of various professions. This platform includes interactive activities and short stories about professions for children.

Germany: Digital toys are used to introduce children to engineering and scientific research fields. For example, through "LEGO Education" tools, children acquire basic skills in engineering and technology.

South Korea: Virtual laboratories develop children's ability to conduct scientific experiments. Additionally, students are provided with opportunities to explore professions through special "AR (augmented reality)" technologies.

National Experience: In Uzbekistan, mobile applications and interactive multimedia lessons created under the state program "Ilk Qadam" broaden children's understanding of professions. For instance, through the program "Milliy Kasblar Olami", children are introduced to professions that align with their culture and traditions.

2. Pedagogical Significance of the Cultural-Humanistic Approach

The cultural-humanistic approach is aimed at increasing social responsibility, not only in children but also in educators themselves.

Foreign Experience:

Finland: In order to develop children's interest in professions in harmony with cultural values, the "Culture and Labor" project is implemented in kindergartens. Through this project, children are introduced to professions that align with their cultural environments.

Japan: Digital animation materials are used to introduce children to business culture and traditional handicraft professions.

National Experience: Professions such as craftsmanship and agriculture, which are an inseparable part of our culture, are taught to children in preschool education through digital materials. For example, profession-introducing videos or handicraft games convey national values to children.

3. Methodology for Developing Professional-Pedagogical Culture in Future Educators

Using digital technologies is one of the most effective methods for shaping professional-pedagogical culture in future educators:

Interactive Seminars: Foreign educational programs organize seminars that teach the use of digital tools.

Project-Based Learning: Educators develop virtual games and lesson materials that align with children's needs.

Foreign Experience:

Canada: Remote teaching methods and digital education platforms are used in training future educators. They learn advanced methods of teaching children.

Singapore: Special training sessions are conducted on creating and using profession-related digital games in educator training.

National Experience: Courses on "Fundamentals of Digital Pedagogy" are organized for educators, where they are taught how to create digital resources and use them in the educational process.

Conclusion

Digital technologies play a crucial role in developing children's interest in professions and enhancing the pedagogical skills of educators in preschool education. By integrating foreign and national experiences, it is possible to organize the educational process effectively. This approach not only improves the quality of education but also contributes to the holistic development of both children and educators.

Recommendations

Develop digital programs tailored to the formation of children's interest in professions, based on foreign experiences in Uzbekistan.

Organize training for educators on the use of cultural-humanistic approaches and digital technologies.

Create special multimedia materials that combine foreign and national educational programs.

By implementing these proposals in practice, it will be possible to elevate the quality of preschool education to a new level.

In conclusion, the integration of digital technologies in fostering career interests among preschool-aged children, coupled with the professional development of future educators through a cultural-humanistic approach, presents a holistic strategy for enhancing early childhood education. This methodology not only empowers young learners to explore various career possibilities in an engaging manner but also ensures that educators are well-equipped to nurture these interests in a supportive environment. By bridging the gap between children's aspirations and educators' competencies, this approach lays a strong foundation for lifelong learning and adaptability, ultimately contributing to the development of well-rounded individuals ready to thrive in an ever-evolving world.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedova, N. (2020). *Digital Technologies and Their Role in the Education System*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan National University Press.
2. Amraeva, G., & Karomatov, T. (2022). *Methodology for Developing Interest in Professions in Preschool Education*. Tashkent: Science and Technology.
3. Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung. (2019). *Digital Media in Education*. Retrieved from: <https://www.bpb.de>
4. Andreeva, N. (2018). *Innovative Educational Technologies and Methodology*. Moscow: Tsinggauer Publishing.
5. Frolova, L., & Karpov, A. (2021). *Cultural and Humanitarian Approach in Education: Global Practices*. *Journal of Educational Innovations*, 29(4), 18–34.
6. American Psychological Association. (2019). *The Digital Revolution and Education: Educational Technology and Its Impact on Youth*. Retrieved from: <https://www.apa.org>
7. EduTech Group. (2020). *Interactive Learning Platforms: An International Comparison*. Berlin: EduTech Publishing.
8. Finke, C., & Volckmar, S. (2020). *Digital Learning Methods and Career Development for Children*. London: Routledge.
9. UNESCO. (2021). *Global Education Monitoring Report 2021: Digital Learning and Equity*. Retrieved from: <https://www.unesco.org>
10. Karimov, J. (2021). *Digital Technologies and Cultural Values in the National Education System*. Tashkent: Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
11. Clark, B., & Jones, A. (2021). *Virtual Career Exploration for Children: Global Insights*. *Journal of Digital Learning*, 22(6), 11-22.